

*UTC-UTI YEAR 4 CONFERENCE PUBLICATIONS (4/2020 to 9/2020)*

*Selected Conference Papers and Presentations:*

01. Alexander, G., Gutierrez, M., Krajnovich, A. and Harelson, S. (2020). "Calibration of a Numerical Model of the Eisenhower-Johnson Memorial Tunnel Pilot Bore by Back Analysis," 54th US Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium, Golden, Colorado June 28 – July 1, 2020, ARMA 20–1217, 9 pp.
02. Arora, K., Cruz, E.C.V., Gutierrez, M. and Hedayat, A. (2020). "Characterization of Synthetic Mudstone for Physical Model Studies," 54th US Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium, Golden, Colorado June 28 – July 1, 2020, ARMA 20–1986, 8 pp.
03. Caspar, J., Bravo, J., Wang, S., Abdulridha, A., Neti, S., Romero, C., Naito, C., Sulieman, M., Quiel, S., Yao, Z. and Oztekin, A. (2020), "Thermal Performance of Sensible Energy Storage Module Consisting of a Cementitious Matrix- the Effect of Operating Conditions," ASME 2020 Heat Transfer Summer Conference, SHTC 2020-12361, July 12 - 16, 2020, Orlando, FL, USA.
04. Gangrade, R., Trainor-Guitton, W. and Mooney, M. (2020). An Integrated Framework to Optimize Site Investigations for Tunneling Applications. ITA-AITES World Tunnels Congress, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Sept 15-21, 2020.
05. Grasmick, J., Maxwell, A., Mooney, M. and Gangrade R. (2020) Probabilistic Subsurface Modeling in Tunneling Applications: Is it Useful? ITA-AITES World Tunnels Congress, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Sept 15-21, 2020.
06. Gutierrez, M. and Xu, G. (2020). "Study on the Damage Evolution in Secondary Tunnel Lining Under the Combined Actions of Corrosion Degradation of Preliminary Support and Creep Deformation of Surrounding Rock," ITA-AITES World Tunnel Congress, WTC2020 and 46th General Assembly, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia 15-21 May 2020.
07. Krajnovic, A., Zhou, W. and Gutierrez, M. (2020). "Uncertainty Assessment of Fault Networks in 3D Geologic Models of Mountain Tunnels," ITA-AITES World Tunnel Congress, WTC2020 and 46th General Assembly, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia 15-21 May 2020.
08. Krajnovich, A., Zhou, W. and Gutierrez, M. (2020). "Characterizing Fault Zone Structure and Geometry using Photogrammetry and 3D Geologic Modeling," 54th US Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium, Golden, Colorado June 28 – July 1, 2020. ARMA 20–1762, 7 pp.
09. Naito, C. (2020), "Construction and Field Evaluation of Electrically Isolated Tendons in a Precast/Prestressed/Post-Tensioned Concrete Spliced Girder Bridge - Coplay Bridge (S.R. 704)," ATLSS Report No. 20-03, ATLSS Center, Lehigh University, April 2020.
10. Wang, S., Abdulridha, A., Quiel, S., Naito, C., Sulieman, M., Caspar, J., Bravo, J., Neti, S., Romero, C., Yao, Z. and Oztekin, A. (2020), "Mechanical Performance of Concrete Thermal Energy Storage Subject to Operating Thermal Demands," ASME 2020 Heat Transfer Summer Conference, SHTC 2020-12369, July 12 - 16, 2020, Orlando, FL, USA.
11. Xu, G. and Gutierrez, M. (2020). "Modeling of Creep and Nonlinear Damage Effects in Rocks and Application to Tunneling," ISRM International Symposium Eurock 2020, Norway, June 14-19, 2020.